

Results and Discussion

Substitution of chlorine atom of *N*-methyl-2-chloroacetoacetamide (**1**) by a nucleophile is not possible because of presence of mesomeric anion of *N*-methyl-2-chloroacetoacetamide (**1**). Probably, the negative charge on both the carbonyl oxygens makes carbon-2 atom as an anion. Therefore, a nucleophilic substitution is possible on the carbonyl carbon atom to give the corresponding chloro enamines.

From the pmr spectra it was seen that the chloro enamines (**3**) were a mixture of (*Z*)- and (*E*)-isomers. Only (*Z*)-isomers of the compounds (sl. nos. 1–9) were isolated from the total product.

In the ir spectra of the chloro enamines (sl. nos. 1–9) the double bond stretching appears as a strong band at 1600–1620 cm^{-1} . The high extinction coefficient for this absorption may be attributed to the overlap between the electron pair on the nitrogen atom and the π -electrons of the double bond.

References

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Synthesis of Azomethines of Anthrone

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A new series of azomethines have been prepared by condensing anthrone with different primary amines, *o*-aminophenol and *p*-aminobenzoic acid (**1**) and (ii) nitrosonaphthols (**2**). A new compound 10-*p*-aminobenzylidene anthrone was also synthesised which was condensed with aldehydes and ketones to give one more new series of azomethines (**3**). Anticancer activity of all the compounds was studied.

Experimental

The m.p.s. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The structures were supported by elemental analysis and ir spectra (KBr).

Azomethines of the anthrone (1): The compounds were prepared from different primary amines, *o*-aminophenol and *p*-aminobenzoic acid (Table 1). Equimolar (0.01 mol) quantities of the anthrone and the respective primary amine or *o*-aminophenol or *p*-aminobenzoic acid taken in methanol or ethanol (25–30 ml) and glacial acetic acid (2–3 drops), were refluxed for 3 h and then allowed to cool overnight. The resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from methanol or ethanol; ν_{max} 1660 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Azomethines of the anthrone (2): The compounds were prepared from α - and β -nitrosonaphthols. Equimolar (0.01 mol) quantities of the anthrone and the respective nitrosonaphthol (prepared by standard methods¹) in methanol or ethanol (25–30 ml) were refluxed for 3 h. It was then poured hot on crushed ice and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from 30% aqueous ethanol; ν_{max} 1660 (C=N) and 1680 cm^{-1} (C=O) (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	Ar/R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1a	C_6H_5-	202	70	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}$
1b	$p\text{-NO}_2-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$	167	65	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$
1c	$o\text{-CH}_3-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$	169	67	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}$
1d	$o\text{-OCH}_3-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$	212	65	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$
1e	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{CH}_2-$	225	55	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}$
1f	Naphthyl	194	65	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}$
1g	$o\text{-OH}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$	192	70	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}$
1h	$p\text{-HOOC}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$	168	60	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2$

(Table 1 contd.)

3a	$C_6H_5CH=$ H_2C	277	55	$C_{29}H_{19}NO$
3b	H_2C H_2C	235	60	$C_{24}H_{19}NO$
3c	C_6H_5 C_6H_5	194	60	$C_{29}H_{21}NO$
3d	$O_6H_5-CH=CH-$	230	50	$C_{20}H_{21}NO$
3e		239	40	$C_{26}H_{17}NO_2$

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

Azomethines of 10-p-aminobenzylidene anthrone :

10-p-Aminobenzylidene anthrone : 10-p-Nitrobenzylidene anthrone (3.27 g, 0.01 mol ; prepared by the reported method^a) was refluxed with SnCl₂ (8 g) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) and concentrated HCl (20 ml) was added for 0.5 h. The reflux was continued for further 3 h and the hot reaction mixture was poured slowly with stirring in ice-cold 40% NaOH solution (100 ml). The copious precipitate was digested in the ether solution to remove excess SnCl₂ and filtered hot and washed free of NaOH by water. The resulting solid was dried and crystallised from aqueous ethanol (50%) (Found : C, 84.14 ; H, 5.03 ; N, 4.7. Calcd. for : C, 84.85 ; H, 5.05 ; N, 4.71%). The presence of the primary amine was confirmed by diazotisation of the compound to produce an orange coloured dye.

Azomethines of 10-p-aminobenzylidene anthrone (3) : A new series of azomethines were prepared by condensing different aldehydes and ketones with 10-p-aminobenzylidene anthrone. 10-p-Aminobenzylidene anthrone (0.295 g, 0.001 mol) was refluxed for 3 h with equimolar quantity of the respective aldehyde or ketone in methanol or ethanol (15 ml) and glacial acetic acid (1 drop). The hot solution was cooled and kept overnight, and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from methanol or ethanol ; ν_{max} 1 660 (C=N) and 1 680 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

Anticancer activity : Anticancer activity tests^a were carried out on P-83 (ovarian) tumor *in situ*. Compounds 1 indicated intense anticancer activity, while compounds 2 and 3 did not show any activity. These facts indicate that the presence of azomethine group stabilised by aromatic ring shows anticancer activity. Azomethine compounds containing C=O or -CH=CH- group or both do not reveal anticancer activity.

References

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Studies on Pyrazolines. Part-II. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 1H-3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-butoxy-5-nitrophen-1''-yl)-5-substituted-phenyl-2-pyrazolines and related Compounds

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IN view of the biological activity of pyrazoline derivatives¹ and in continuation of our earlier work², the synthesis of pyrazolines 2 and their derivatives (3, 4 and 5) was undertaken.

In the present communication previously reported 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcones (1)² on condensation with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol gave 1H-3-(2''-hydroxy-3''-bromo-4''-n-butoxy-5''-nitrophen-1''-yl)-5-substituted-phenyl-2-pyrazolines (2). The reaction of 2 with benzoyl chloride gave the benzoyl derivatives (3). Similarly, the reaction of 2 with acetic acid gave the acetyl derivatives (4) by direct and indirect methods. Further, the reactions of the pyrazolines (2) with various sulphonyl chlorides afforded the corresponding sulphonamide derivatives (5) (Scheme 1). The structures of the compounds have been supported by elemental and ir spectral data.

The compounds 2 revealed the following ir bands : 2 3 500-3 400 (OH), 3 340-3 320 (NH), 1 620-1 600 (C=N), 1 240-1 220 (C-N) and 1 380-1 370 cm⁻¹ (CH₂ of pyrazoline) ; 3 3 500-3 350 (OH), 1 660-1 650 (C=O, N-C=O), 1 610-1 590 (C=N) and 1 230-1 220 cm⁻¹ (C-N) ; 4 3 500-3 350 (OH), 1 670-1 660 (C=O, N-C=O), 1 615-1 600 (C=N) and 1 230-1 220 cm⁻¹ (C-N) ; 5 3 500-3 350 (OH), 1 610-1 600 (C=N), 1 300-1 290, 1 145-1 140 (S=O sym and asym, respectively) and 1 230-1 220 cm⁻¹ (C-N).

The compounds exhibited pmr peaks at : 2 δ 3.00-3.20 (1H, dd, CH₂ of pyrazoline ring), 3.60-3.80 (1H, dd, CH₂ of pyrazoline ring), 4.80-5.10 (1H, dd, CH of pyrazoline ring) and 6.8-8.1 (m, ArH and NH), integration of signals at δ 3.0-5.1 (CHCH₂ group of pyrazoline ring) ; 3 δ 2.8-3.6 (CH₂ of pyrazoline ring), 4.90-5.20 (CH of pyrazoline ring) and 7.45-8.5 (ArH) ; 4 δ 2.7-3.5 (CH₂ of pyrazoline ring), 4.8-5.1 (CH of pyrazoline ring) and 7.30-8.3 (ArH) ; 5 δ 3.0-3.8 CH₂ of pyrazoline ring), 5.0-5.3 (CH of pyrazoline ring) 7.50-8.6 (ArH).